

NDAC/LO/003

1982 May 24

Remarks on the Process Definitions1. Introduction

Within the Northern Data Analysis Consortium it is the responsibility of Lund Observatory to define the analytical processes and data interfaces of all software subsystems having a direct bearing on the astrometric accuracy. This task comprises more specifically the eight work packages listed below with dates of completion according to present planning.

WP	NAME	TARGET DATE
1100	Preprocessing of SM Data (Definition)	1982 Nov 30
2100	Attitude Reconstitution (Definition)	1982 Dec 31
3100	Preprocessing of IDT Data (Definition)	1982 Sep 30
4100	Location Estimator (Definition)	1982 Oct 31
5100	Set Solution (Definition)	1982 Jun 30
6100	PRS Solution (Definition)	1983 Feb 28
7100	Back-Substitution (Definition)	1983 Apr 30
8100	Double Stars (Definition)	1983 Aug 31

The definition of a process should provide the information necessary for the subsequent algorithm development phase to be carried out almost independently of other subsystems and by the relevant experts, who are not always completely familiar with the overall software system and the specific problems of

the other processes. The definition phase will therefore have to purposes:

- (i) to describe the analytical models and tools deemed necessary for the desired accuracy, i.e. to define the content of the process; and
- (ii) to delimit the process against other processes or catalogues, i.e. to define its extent.

The working papers giving the results of the definition WP's accordingly consist of a verbal and mathematical process description, followed by a set of Data Interface Descriptions (DID).

2. Process Descriptions

The process descriptions should explain the principles and terminology of the process, summarize the relevant input and output data, and give a complete listing of the basic equations, if possible with references to Annex A of the NDAC Proposal.

The analytical models aim at including all predictable or modelizable effects exceeding 0.1 mas and using efficient estimation methods. There are however many instances where a proper model cannot be given at present. We do not know, for example, the time scales over which the different optical distortion terms will vary, or the characteristic components of the attitude motion. To insist on full generality in these and other respects would bring about a lot of (unnecessary) complications. Whenever such uncertainties come into the picture, the simplest model compatible with known facts will be preferred. This seems to be the only way, given the very limited manpower and time available, to get the development phases started in time. On the other hand it means that the process definitions cannot be definitive, and a reasonable flexibility must be kept throughout the development phases and perhaps even during implementation.

3. Data Interface Descriptions

In principle each arrow in the data flow diagram, Fig. 3.4 in the Proposal, merits a DID. In cases where the data flow from one process to the next is purely sequential (e.g. grid coordinates from the Location Estimator to the Set Solution), one DID is however sufficient as interface between the two processes. In other cases where reordering of data is required, e.g. of abscissae between the Set Solution and the PRS Solution, an intermediate catalogue is assumed to exist, and different DID's are used for its input and output.

Each DID is thus defined by its source and destination (each of which may be a process or a catalogue) and is also given a number, e.g. DID1, DID2. An example of the DID format is given on next page (DID2). The different columns are explained below.

Designation

An alphanumeric designation is given to each data item. This adheres to standard FORTRAN conventions, e.g. at most six characters, first character is I-N for an integer; up to three indices allowed. Although other designations may of course be preferred internally to a process, the ones given here are suggested for all external identification of data.

Annex_A

This column gives, when possible, the corresponding notation in Annex A of the Proposal, and a reference to the page where it is first used.

Explanation

A very short description of the datum is given. This may also serve as a glossary, since some care is taken to use consistent and unique terms.

Concerning the use of identification numbers (object, frame, set, etc), see Section 4 below.

DESIGNATION	ANNEX A	EXPLANATION	UNIT	MIN	RANGE MAX	DEF	PAGE : 1 OF 1 DATE : 82.05.05		
							NUM ABS	ACC REL	DIG-ITS
IFRAME	-	1. <u>For each frame:</u> frame identification number	-	1	$9 \cdot 10^8$	-	1	-	9
TMID	t_K (p31)	frame mid-time	s	0	$2 \cdot 10^8$	-	10^{-6}	-	15
RAZ	α_z (p6)	Right Ascension of z axis	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	-	12
DECZ	δ_z (p6)	Declination of z axis	rad	$-\frac{1}{2}\pi$	$\frac{1}{2}\pi$	-	10^{-9}	-	10
ARGZ	ω (p6)	argument of x axis	rad	$-\pi$	π	-	10^{-11}	-	12

Unit

Using a single, simple, and consistent set of units for all interfaces must be a great advantage. The system proposed here is based on SI for time and distance and the radian for angles. Thus parallaxes are given in rad, proper motions in rad/s, and the barycentric velocity of the satellite in m/s. Conversion to conventional astronomical units (sexagesimal angles, p.m. per year, etc.) is motivated only for display purposes and of course for the various output catalogues.

Range

This gives the normal range of the variable (MIN, MAX), and in some cases a default value (DEF) usually signifying the loss of all relevant information.

Numerical Accuracy

In most cases an absolute representation accuracy is given; in a few cases the relative accuracy is more appropriate. The numbers are usually derived from the requirement that truncation errors shall correspond to angles less than 0.01 mas on the sky.

Digits

This is the minimum number of significant digits required to represent the data with the range and numerical accuracy as in the preceding columns. One or two additional digits are in fact often desirable in view of the risk of accumulating rounding errors.

4. Identification NumbersObject Identification Number (ID)

It is assumed that each star (or quasar, or galaxy) is given a unique, positive, integer number with up to 8 digits (this will presumably be defined by the Input Catalogue Consortium). The first digit (multiple of 10^7) may be reserved for identifying different object classes.

For asteroids (ID number starting with 9), a special system is proposed which allows them to be treated as much as possible in exactly the same way as extraplanetary objects. The planet is formally given a new object identification number each time it appears in either of the FOV's (since its motion can be considered linear during a 20 s apparition). Given that the asteroid number (IDAST) is at most 4 digits and that it may appear at most about 300 times in a 3 year mission, we propose the designation

$$ID = 9aaaaabbb$$

where aaaa = IDAST and bbb = apparition number. Thus, object number 90532065 would be the 65:th apparition of Herculina (532).

Frame Identification Number (IFRAME)

A frame is a collection of IDT and gyro data obtained within a limited time interval of typically 2 s duration (it may be variable). From the data analysis point of view, the only excuse for this concept is the necessity to relate various data to discrete and suitably spaced time instances, given by the frame mid-times (TMID), for the formation of observation equations. The NDAC-frames, assigned during the Preprocessing of IDT Data, need not be related neither to the physical format on which data arrive, nor to the IDT piloting strategy. If the latter is regular and with a cycle time compatible with the above requirements, it may of course still be advantageous to assign NDAC-frames accordingly.

As the data analysis proceeds (Preprocessing of IDT Data, Location Estimator, and Set Solution), the various stages of processed data will also be collected in frames. Since the frame identification number identifies a collection of data (and not the corresponding time interval), frames at the different stages or even different updates of them should have different numbers. The frame mid-time (TMID) is therefore always necessary to identify its place in the mission.

Set Identification Number (ISET)

Similar considerations apply as for IFRAME, except that ISET are assigned by the Set Solution/Control and Monitoring process and refer to data collections covering about 12 h observations.

5. Time

As already mentioned, the unit of time should be the SI second. The required absolute timing accuracy is set by the relative motions in the Solar System: e.g. 0.1 mas apparent motion of a typical asteroid takes about 10 ms. (For computing stellar aberration the requirement is less stringent, since the acceleration of the satellite is $< 0.3 \text{ m s}^{-2}$ and 0.1 mas corresponds to $\Delta v = 0.15 \text{ m s}^{-1}$.)

It is assumed that the data received from ESOC are properly time-tagged, so that the TDT (say) of every photometric or gyroscopic sample can be derived to a fraction of a ms. A unique time scale (for the data analysis) should be defined from an arbitrary origin shortly before launch. E.g. if launch is in early 1987, a convenient origin may be

$$\begin{aligned} \text{TSTART} &= \text{JD } 2446800.0 \\ &= 1987 \text{ Jan } 04.5 \text{ (TDT)} \end{aligned}$$

The frame mid-times (TMID) etc are expressed in seconds from this instant. The representation accuracy should be at least 10^{-5} s .

For the astrometric parameters in the Star Catalogue it is also necessary to define a common epoch (TEPOCH) to which the positions α_0, δ_0 in particular are referred. Again the choice is quite arbitrary, although it may be computationally slightly advantageous to have TEPOCH near the mid-time of mission, some 500 days after TSTART. It should be noted however that the five astrometric parameters (including mean errors) can easily be transformed to any desired epoch, and without any loss of information, provided that the covariance (5-by-5 matrix) is retained.

In the final Star Catalogue a different epoch will probably be chosen as near as possible to the actual mean time of observation (thus minimising correlation between positions and proper motions). Whether a common epoch can be adopted for the entire catalogue, or (as proposed by FAST) epochs are computed for individual stars, should be discussed and agreed upon between the consortia.

Finally for defining the global reference system, the date of the equator and equinox must be specified. This should be the new standard $J2000.0 = JED\ 2451545.0 = 2000\ \text{Jan}\ 1.5\ (\text{TDT})$.